

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

Prof. dr Petar Bulat

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- *President of the 13th STC Congress*

Petar Bulat

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- *President of the CSC*
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ODREĐIVANJE POLICIKLIČNIH AROMATIČNIH UGLJOVODONIKA U SUSPENDOVANIM ČESTICAMA PM₁₀ U VAZDUHU NA TERITORIJI GRADA NOVOG SADA

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Frakcije u vazduhu suspendovanih čestica koje mogu imati najveći efekat na zdravlje ljudi su fine čestice PM₁₀ i PM_{2,5}, čiji su konstituenti i policiklični aromatični ugljovodonici (PAH). Hronična izloženost PAH-ovima može dovesti do negativnih zdravstvenih efekata, uključujući povećan rizik od karcinoma. U okviru monitoringa kvaliteta vazduha na teritoriji Grada Novog Sada, u periodu oktobar 2021.–mart 2022. god. kontinualno su uzorkovane suspendovane čestice PM₁₀ na odabranim fiksnim lokacijama: prigradsko-saobraćajna, osnovna urbana, urbano-saobraćajna, osnovna ruralna i industrijska stanica. Za određivanje koncentracije 16 EPA PAH primenjena je GC/MS tehnika nakon ultrazvučne ekstrakcije PM₁₀ smešom aceton:heksan. Koncentracije ukupnih PAH-ova u suspendovanim česticama PM₁₀ kretale su se od 18 ng/m³ (novembar 2021.) na mernom mestu osnovne urbane stanice, do 35 ng/m³ (januar 2022.) na mernom mestu prigradsko saobraćajne stanice.

Maksimalne prosečne koncentracije pojedinačnih PAH kongenera u analiziranom vremenskom periodu na osnovnoj urbanoj i osnovnoj ruralnoj stanici dostigle su vrednosti od 2.5-3 ng/m³, na urbano saobraćajnoj i industrijskoj do 3-4 ng/m³, dok su na prigradskoj saobraćajnoj stanici prelazile 4 ng/m³. Na osnovu dominantnog prisustva PAH-ova sa 4 i 5 prstenova (BaA, Flu, CHR, suma BbkFA) zaključeno je da primarni izvor emisije PAH-ova u Gradu Novom Sadu čini saobraćaj. Primenom TEF metodologije izračunat je toksični potencijal kvantifikovanih 16 EPA PAH i utvrđeno da najveći doprinos ukupnoj karcinogenoj aktivnosti smeše PAH daje benzo(a)piren, sa udelom od 69% do 73%. Procena izloženosti benzo(a)pirenu (ILCR= 9.0x10⁻⁸ - 3.6x10⁻⁷) pokazala je da je rizik od karcinoma usled inhalatorne izloženosti odrasle populacije BaP-u u vazduhu na teritoriji Grada Novog Sada zanemarljiv.

KLJUČNE REČI: monitoring vazduha, policiklični aromatični ugljovodonici, procena rizika, Novi Sad

DETERMINATION OF POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS IN SUSPENDED PARTICLES PM₁₀ IN THE AIR ON THE TERRITORY OF THE CITY OF NOVI SAD

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The fractions of air suspended particles that could have the greatest effect on human health are fine particles PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are their ubiquitous constituents. Chronic exposure to PAHs consequently causes a series of adverse health effects, including increased risk of cancer. As part of air quality monitoring in the City of Novi Sad, in the period October 2021 - March 2022, suspended PM₁₀ were continuously sampled at selected fixed locations: suburban-traffic, basic urban, urban-traffic, basic rural and industrial stations.

Concentrations of 16 EPA PAHs were determined using GC/MS, after ultrasonic extraction with acetone:hexane mixture. The concentrations of total PAHs ranged from 18ng/m³ (November 2021) at the basic urban station, to 35ng/m³ (January 2022) at the suburban traffic station. The maximum average concentrations of individual PAH congeners at the basic urban and basic rural stations reached 2.5-3ng/m³, at the urban traffic and industrial stations 3-4ng/m³, and exceeded 4ng/m³ at the suburban traffic station. Based on the dominant presence of 4 and 5 rings PAHs (BaA, Flu, CHR, sum BbkFA), the primary source of PAH emission was traffic. The toxic potential of 16 EPA PAHs was calculated using the TEF methodology. Benzo(a)pyrene exhibited the greatest contribution to the total carcinogenic activity of the PAH mixture, with a share of 69% to 73%. Assessment of exposure to benzo(a)pyrene (ILCR= 9.0x10⁻⁸ - 3.6x10⁻⁷) showed that risk of cancer due to inhalation exposure of the adult population to BaP in the City of Novi Sad was negligible.

KEYWORDS: air monitoring, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, risk assessment, Novi Sad